

EFFECTIVE WAYS OF TEACHING LIFE SAFETY TO SPECIALISTS OF “AGRICULTURAL MECHANIZATION” IN TECHNICAL HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS IN THE CONDITIONS OF THE CREDIT-MODULE EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM

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Abstract. *This article is based on the development of professional competence in agricultural specialists in the context of the credit-module education system using the “Case Study” method in lecture sessions and “Dual” education in practical sessions in the subject of “Safety of Life Activities”.*

Keywords: *credit, module, safety, agriculture, specialist, case study, dual, enterprise, education, competence, engineer.*

Introduction

At the heart of the reforms being implemented in the education system of our country, the education of young people with modern skills and broad outlook is being put forward as a priority task. The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M.Mirziyoyev, at the event dedicated to the solemn presentation of State Awards, emphasized that “Science is the basis of development. Neither a state nor a society that does not rely on the achievements of modern science and innovative ideas has a future. Only through science and education, intellectual potential, and comprehensively educated personnel can we bring Uzbekistan to a new stage of development”[3], which is of great importance in our training of young specialists today.

After gaining independence in our country, as a result of large-scale reforms, the foundations of our national statehood were strengthened, the sovereignty of our state, the inviolability of our borders were ensured, effective work was carried out to strengthen the atmosphere of peace and tranquility, interethnic harmony and religious tolerance in our society, the rule of law, the realization of human rights and freedoms and interests. One of such works is the development of the “Action Strategy” project for the further development of Uzbekistan. By the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev dated January 28, 2022, as a result of a wide public discussion of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2022-2026, seven strategic goals were developed based on the principle of “From a Strategy of Actions to a Strategy of Development”: building a people-oriented state through the promotion of human dignity and the further development of a free civil society. The following priority areas have been put forward: making the principles of justice and the rule of law the most basic and necessary condition for development in our country; rapidly developing the national economy and ensuring high growth rates; conducting a fair social policy, developing human capital; ensuring spiritual development and bringing the sector to a new level; approaching universal problems based on national interests; strengthening the security and defense potential of our country, conducting an open, pragmatic and active foreign policy[2].

The 30th goal of the decree is: Increasing the income of peasants and farmers by at least 2 times through intensive development of agriculture on a scientific basis, and increasing the annual growth of agriculture to at least 5 percent. Therefore, training future agricultural engineers as qualified personnel is of great importance. This places a great responsibility on higher educational institutions in this area, namely in the technical field.

In particular, today the educational process in higher educational institutions in the technical field has been transferred to the credit-modular education system. We will not be mistaken if we say that the first step towards the transfer to this system was the “Concept for the Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030”[1], approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan PD-5847 dated October 8, 2019.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND METHODS

The issues of training future agricultural engineers as qualified personnel in their chosen specialties, and the development of their professional competence were discussed at different times by scientists of our republic, such as A.Abdukodirov[5]. On the problems of improving the personnel training system from the point of view of professional orientation, and preparing future young specialists for professional activity, the following scientists of our country worked: U.I.Inoyatov, R.H.Jurayev, E.A.Seytxalilov, Sh.E.Qurbonov, A.R.Khodjaboyev, Z.K.Ismoilova, Q.T.Olimov, N.A.Muslimov, S.Q.Qahhorov, D.D.Sharipova, Sh.S.Sharipov, Sh.S.Olimov, J.A.Hamidov, M.B.Orozova, O.T.Turakulov. It has been studied in detail in the scientific research works of D.O.Khimataliev, N.Sh.Shodiyev, F.M.Zakirova, N.I.Taylakov and others[6].

The analysis of the research work conducted by V.G.Bocharova, Yu.A.Galaguzova, S.I.Grigorev, L.G.Guslyakova, I.A.Zimney, N.P.Klushina, R.M.Kulichenko, V.A.Nikitin, N.B.Shmeleva, G.P.Shtinova reveals that the main components of personnel training in higher educational institutions are substantive and procedural.

According to S.Kh.Abdullaev, the personnel training system of higher education in the bachelor's degree program "Mechanization of Agriculture" ensures the professional socialization of future bachelor's degree personnel and includes three components: substantive, technological and subjective.

According to I.F.Isaev, “For modern society, the changes taking place in all aspects of human life and activity, the active development of cultural values objectively require the transformation of higher education into an institution of reproduction and creation of culture. The spiritual potential of highly qualified, intellectual bachelor personnel is manifested in general and professional culture. This potential constitutes national wealth and must be used rationally.”

From the above, it can be understood that the training of agricultural engineers, the formation of knowledge, skills and qualifications in them remains one of the topical issues of today.

In our opinion, in the context of the credit-modular education system, we consider it important to pay attention to the following in the development of the professional competence of agricultural engineers:

Establishing cooperation with specialists from agricultural enterprises in the development of the curriculum of the specialty (formation of compulsory and elective subjects);

Adhering to the credit module requirements when organizing classes in each subject;
 Paying attention to the availability of sufficient textbooks in the specialty;
 Introducing the use of the "Case Study" method in lecture classes, and paying attention to organizing practical classes on the basis of "Dual" education.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Our research was conducted on the example of teaching the subject “Life Safety” among students of the “Agricultural Mechanization” direction in the context of the credit-modular education system in 2023-2025. Initially, the status of student training was determined through an anonymous questionnaire survey. At the first exploratory stage, psychological, pedagogical, and methodological literature on the development of professional competence of future engineers in the context of the credit-modular education system was studied and analyzed. The state of organization and conduct of the educational process on the development of professional competence of future engineers in the context of the credit-modular education system was analyzed and its importance in the process of acquiring professional qualifications was determined. At the initial stage, the following result was determined (see Table 1).

ANONYMOUS SURVEY (Preliminary)

To determine the status of the process of teaching "Life Safety" to students of the "Agricultural Mechanization" major at the Namangan Engineering and Construction Institute under the credit-module education system

№	The content of the situation in providing knowledge to students in life safety lessons	Answers		
		Students' chosen answers and number		
		A total of 38 students		
		yes	no	hesitant
1	Are you taught on a credit-module system?	38	-	-
2	Before starting to study the subject, did the subject teacher explain: the credit allocated to the subject and the process of accumulating credit?	26	3	7
3	Do you know how many modules are in the subject?	17	9	12
4	Were you given the opportunity to choose your science teacher?	-	29	9
5	Do you know how many semesters of training are conducted in this subject?	19	8	11
6	Do you know if this subject is a "Compulsory or Elective Subject"?	13	24	1
7	Do you know how many credits are allocated to this subject in total?	16	13	9

8	Do you have an understanding of assessment in the credit-module system (current, intermediate, independent study, final)?	24	12	4
9	Do you think the science teacher has a sufficient understanding of the credit-module system?	20	13	5
10	Is your attitude towards using the credit-module system in the educational process positive?	13	21	4
11	In your opinion, does using the credit-module system in the educational process have certain advantages?	17	14	7
12	Do you think students should be more active in the context of the credit-module system?	15	20	3
13	Does the science teacher use modern interactive methods during the lesson?	17	13	8
14	Do you know about the case study method?	5	24	9
15	Are you familiar with problem-based learning technology?	6	17	15
16	Do you have a positive opinion about dual education?	14	13	11
17	Are there any advantages to using the "Bliss-Game" method in lessons?	11	17	10
18	In practical and laboratory training, do you learn what to do in the event of an occupational accident?	12	15	11
19	Can this science help you become a true "Occupational Safety Engineer"?	17	18	3

In the conditions of the credit-module education system, the indicators of teaching the subject "Life Safety" (%) are:

1. Compliance with the credit-module education system 43%;
2. Use of modern methods in subject classes (lecture, practical, laboratory) 65%;
3. Adaptation of the subject to the specialty 71%;
4. Positive approach to the credit-module system 48%, negative approach 52%;

After the above result was determined, the syllabus of the subject "Life Safety" was adapted to the conditions of the credit-module education system for students of the "Agricultural Mechanization" direction, and classes were organized using "Case Study" in lecture classes and "Dual" education in practical classes. The following types of "Case Study" method were used:

Type of case used in the training: "Mini" structures:

1. Case (problem) description.
2. Tasks (or questions) for solving the case (problem).
3. List of literature for use.

4. Methodological instructions.
5. The process of solving the case (analysis and putting forward solution options, checking the acceptability of options).
6. Organizing a presentation on the case solution.
7. Analysis of the case solution.
8. Solution of the teacher (caseologist).

The type of case used in the training: "Complex" structures:

1. Pedagogical annotation.
2. Introduction.
3. Description of the case (problem).
4. Tasks (or questions) for solving the case (problem).
5. List of literature for use.
6. Methodological instructions.
7. The process of solving the case (analysis and putting forward solution options, checking the acceptability of the options).
8. Organizing a presentation on the case solution.

Practical training in the subject "Life Safety" was conducted using "Dual" education. The process of organizing "Dual" education is as follows:

1. Signing a mutual agreement with an enterprise related to the specialty. According to it, preparing an audience and hiring an experienced employee to organize a practical training at the enterprise;
2. Organizing practical, laboratory training in the subject;
3. Conducting qualification practices;
4. Performing independent learning of subject assignments (to be completed at the enterprise).

At the end of our research, an anonymous questionnaire was conducted among students of the "Agricultural Mechanization" direction in order to check the status of teaching the subject "Life Safety" in the context of the credit-modular education system (see Table 2).

To determine the status of the process of teaching "Life Safety" to students of the "Agricultural Mechanization" direction at the Namangan Engineering and Construction Institute under the credit-module education system

ANONYMOUS SURVEY (At the end of the pilot work)

№	The content of the situation in providing knowledge to students in life safety lessons	Answers		
		Students' chosen answers and number		
		A total of 38 students		
		yes	no	hesitant
1	Are you taught on a credit-module system?	38	-	-
2	Before starting to study the subject, did the subject teacher explain: the credit allocated to	38	-	-

	the subject and the process of accumulating credit?			
3	Do you know how many modules are in the subject?	38	-	-
4	Were you given the opportunity to choose your science teacher?	38	-	-
5	Do you know how many semesters of training are conducted in this subject?	26	5	7
6	Do you know if this subject is a "Compulsory or Elective Subject"?	29	3	6
7	Do you know how many credits are allocated to this subject in total?	38	-	-
8	Do you have an understanding of assessment in the credit-module system (current, intermediate, independent study, final)?	38	-	-
9	Do you think the science teacher has a sufficient understanding of the credit-module system?	38	-	-
10	Is your attitude towards using the credit-module system in the educational process positive?	28	7	3
11	In your opinion, does using the credit-module system in the educational process have certain advantages?	27	5	6
12	Do you think students should be more active in the context of the credit-module system?	26	2	10
13	Does the science teacher use modern interactive methods during the lesson?	33	-	5
14	Do you know about the case study method?	34	-	4
15	Are you familiar with problem-based learning technology?	31	-	7
16	Do you have a positive opinion about dual education?	17	3	18
17	Are there any advantages to using the "Bliss-Game" method in lessons?	23	6	9
18	In practical and laboratory training, do you learn what to do in the event of an occupational accident?	28	6	4
19	Can this science help you become a true "Occupational Safety Engineer"?	27	-	8

The indicators of teaching the subject "Life Safety" in the conditions of the credit-module education system (%):

- 1. Compliance with the credit-module education system 81%;**
- 2. Use of modern methods in subject classes (lecture, practical, laboratory) 79%;**

3. Adaptation of the subject to the specialty 84%

4. Positive approach to the credit-module system 79%, negative approach 21%

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

In conclusion, it should be noted that in the context of the credit-module education system, when organizing lessons using the "Case Study" method and the "Dual" educational technology, the following positive results can be achieved, the teacher:

1. Ensures that lessons are interesting and meaningful;
2. Ensures that the assessment of students' knowledge in the subject is fair;
3. Helps to acquire knowledge, skills and qualifications for the development of professional competence in specialties;
4. Strengthens theoretical and practical knowledge in the subject, as well as conducts independent educational activities and, on this basis, serves as a practical assistant in strengthening professional qualifications.

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